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The potential role of bananas in spreading rice root-knot nematode, *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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The root-knot nematode, *Meloidogyne graminicola*, is one of the main pests of rice in the Philippines (Prot et al 1993) and other Asian countries (Bridge et al 1990). In the Philippines, this nematode can be found in irrigated as well as in upland rice. Its pathogenic effect, however, is more important on upland and rainfed rice than on irrigated rice (Prot and Matias 1995).

Banana trees are a very common and striking element of the landscape in most rice-growing areas in the Philippines. They are often planted very close to rice fields and are often the only big plants growing on bunds between plots. In Surinam (South America), banana trees have been reported to be a good host for the other rice root-knot nematode, *M. oryzae*. This species, found only in South America at the moment, is very close in taxonomy and biology to *M. graminicola* (Segeren and Sanchit 1984). Therefore, the possibility of banana trees in the Philippines becoming hosts of *M. graminicola* was investigated.

Six suckers of each of three common banana cultivars in the Philippines were obtained from the Institute of Plant Breeding of the University of the Philippines Los Baños. One cultivar was Saba, a cooking banana, and the other two were Lakatan and Latundan, which are sweet bananas. These 18 plants were collected from a nonsterilized soil and therefore were probably contaminated with nematodes. All roots were carefully removed by cutting them with a knife as close as possible

to the corm. The number of leaves of each banana tree was reduced to two or three. The surface area of these remaining leaves was reduced by cutting them to half their length to reduce transpiration and to avoid their drying before new roots grow. Each plant was replanted in a bucket with the appropriate amount of pasteurized soil, from 8.5 to 30 L, depending on the size of the sucker. Five weeks later, the suckers resumed growth, as evidenced by the development of new leaves.

Each bucket was inoculated with 10,000 infective juveniles (J2) of *M. graminicola* (strain I-LB of the IRRI nematology laboratory), recovered from infested roots of rice with the help of a mistifier. Ten weeks after inoculation, the banana trees were uprooted and the roots were examined to detect the presence of galls. The roots were then placed in the mistifier for 2 wk for nematode extraction. Each root sample was weighed (fresh weight) at the end of the extraction period.

Roots of the 18 banana suckers, recovered before replanting

for inoculation, were found to be infested with nematodes specific to banana (Gowen and Queneherve 1990): *Radopholus similis* and *Helicotylenchus multicinctus*, but also *Hoplolaimus* spp. and *Meloidogyne* spp. To rapidly check the group of *Meloidogyne* coming from these initial roots, nematodes obtained from each sucker were inoculated on one pot planted with rice (UPLRi5) and one pot planted with tobacco. These pots were maintained in the glasshouse for 5 wk and the roots were collected for examination. There were no galls at all on rice or on tobacco. This result demonstrated that the native *Meloidogyne* extracted from banana roots was neither *M. graminicola* nor *M. incognita*.

Roots of banana trees were harvested 10 wk after inoculation with *M. graminicola*: they were severely galled and important populations of second-stage juveniles of *Meloidogyne* were recovered from the mistifier (see table). Since the size of the suckers was quite variable within each cultivar (3–12 kg), the range of root population and root weight was

Final population of nematodes extracted from roots of banana trees cut out 10 wk after inoculation with 10,000 infective juveniles of *Meloidogyne graminicola* (numbers per sample; mean and range: max and min; six replications of each cultivar).

Nematode species		Cultivars		
		Saba	Lakatan	Latundan
<i>Meloidogyne graminicola</i>	Mean	92,000	74,580	17,630
	Min	29,500	36,500	5,500
	Max	272,800	124,000	24,500
<i>Radopholus similis</i>	Mean	0	35,700	0
	(min-max)		(106–162,000)	
Fresh root weight of sample (g)	Mean	476	228	184
	(min-max)	(116–1,533)	(172–353)	(91–246)